

Balinese Language Learning Media “Satua I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah” For Elementary School Students

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Article History

Received: 18.09.2024
Accepted: 09.10.2024
Published: 22.10.2024

Abstract: Literature lives orally, that is, literature that is spread in an unwritten form conveyed by oral means from generation to generation. One of the existing Balinese folktales (satua) is Katuturan I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah. This satua is one of the cultural heritages of the Balinese people that has character education values that can be an initial formula for providing character education and learning local languages. The method used in this research is the ADDIE method: analysis, design, development, and implementation. Assisted by government facilities in the form of laptops for students, researchers can create interactive multimedia learning. The main feature of this interactive multimedia is that users can enjoy the illustration of Satua Bali's "I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah" with various other features such as animation, games, and voice narration. This research results in a Windows-based interactive multimedia application for Satua Bali "I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah".

Keywords: Balinese Language, Learning Media, Digital Media, Satua, I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah, Digital Culture.

Cite this article:

Mutiarani, R. A., Majida, M., Arnawa, I. N., Sudipa, I. G. I., Putra, P. S. U., (2024). Balinese Language Learning Media “Satua I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah” For Elementary School Students. *ISAR Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(10), 32-36.

Introduction

Regional language is one of the self-identities of a nation. Including ethnic Balinese people who have the Balinese language, a means and vehicle for cultural life, religion, and sustainable customs until now. The preservation of Balinese language is being intensively planned by the government for the development of Balinese language, script, and literature. On April 10, 2018, the Bali Provincial DPRD authorized the issuance of regional regulation Number 1 of 2018 concerning "Development of Balinese Language, Script, and Literature (Duija & PF, 2019; Pratama, 2019).

One of the fosterings of Balinese language, script, and literature is Satua Bali, which is a traditional Balinese literary heritage intended for children and contains moral values for the formation of children's character. Literature lives orally, that is, literature that is spread in unwritten form and conveyed by oral means from generation to generation. One of the existing Balinese satua is Katuturan I Kedis Sangsiah Teken I Bojog. One aini is found in the fifth grade guidebook for public elementary schools and can be a source of strengthening character in children. In addition, mesatua can also be an interesting model and method for fostering the language literacy of elementary students in particular (Aditama et al., 2022; Diari, 2020).

The author analyses and compiles research with data obtained through the research method of research and development type with the ADDIE model. This research was chosen with the

title "Interactive Multimedia-Based Learning Media Satua Bali I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah for Elementary School Students". Interactive media will be made desktop-based and support laptop media facilities from SDN 03 Sempidi. It is hoped that learning Balinese using interactive media can be implemented. According to (Limbong & Simarmata, 2020; Priyono et al., 2023; I. N. T. A. Putra et al., 2021; Sudipa et al., 2022; Yuliasih et al., 2023), examples of interactive multimedia are interactive learning, game applications, etc. Multimedia-based interactive learning media is used to channel messages (knowledge, skills, and attitudes) and can stimulate the choices, feelings, attention, and willingness of students so that the learning process deliberately occurs, is purposeful, and is controlled. Therefore, it is hoped that the interactive multimedia developed can help students in terms of interest and the current way of learning (Kurniawan et al., 2024; Mamis et al., 2023; Mutiarani & Mahayoni, 2023; Yusa et al., 2023)

Method

The research method used in this research is the research and development research method. Development research is a research method used to produce certain products and test the effectiveness of these products. Research and development is a process or method used to validate and develop products (Çeken & Taşkın, 2022; Ibrahim et al., 2023; Ijaz, 2018; Yanti et al., 2023). The procedure in the research consists of the first stage (Analysis), which is to analyze the needs of animation material, student characteristics, software analysis, and specification analysis. The

second stage is designing (Design) which consists of making animation storyboards, compiling material and evaluation questions, and making media backgrounds, images, and buttons in the application. The third stage is the Development stage, which consists of making interactive animated media, media validation, and media revision. The fourth stage is Implementation, which is the media testing and evaluation stage. Then the final product is obtained in the form of learning media in the form of applications (Prasetyo et al., 2020) . The research method is called the ADDIE method, which can be interpreted as a scientific way to research, design, produce, and test the validity of the products that have been produced. Aims to produce new products and test the effectiveness of these products (I. N. A. S. Putra & Mudra, 2022; I. N. T. A. Putra et al., 2021; Yuliasih et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Design Scheme

In this phase, the author carried out data collection in the form of questionnaires and pretests targeted at students in SDN 03 Sempidi V class of 26 students, to evaluate their ability to understand the Bali language. The data is used as a measure of the success of the interactive media offered.

According to the initial student questionnaire results, 85% of students experience challenges in learning Balinese Alus, 92% indicate that Balinese instruction relies solely on textbooks, 77% report the use of uniform teaching methods in Balinese education, 65% find Balinese learning enjoyable, while 35% perceive it as tedious. Additionally, 62% of students express a desire to enhance Balinese teaching methods, 50% have engaged with Balinese content outside of textbooks, and 88% are unable to comprehend Balinese Alus vocabulary through auditory and reading methods alone. Sixty-two percent of students comprehend English more proficiently than Balinese, seventy-three percent of students assessed the Balinese learning technique as good, and one hundred percent of students recognized the significance of acquiring Balinese as their indigenous language.

Informed by the outcomes of the second student questionnaire, the solution was formulated by equipping learning environments with interactive multimedia for the study of Satua Bali. 85% of students desire supplementary illustrations and translations into Indonesian that are customized to their preferences and requirements. Students

are expected to engage actively in learning, facilitating comprehension and fostering creativity for an enjoyable educational experience, particularly in contrast to the acquisition of other languages. The development of this interactive multimedia is hindered by the absence of educational media necessary for assessing and analyzing the content of each component.

Table 1: Student Pretest Score using Balinese Language

No	Question	Total	%
1	Napi bantang satua I Bojog teken I Sangsiah?	0	0%
2	Sedek ngudiang I Sangsiah tepukina tekén IBojog?	26	50%
3	Napi sane kaangen kedis sangsiah ngaé sebun?	14	27%
4	Apa krana I Bojog orahanga belog?	11	21%
5	Ngudiang dadi I Bojog pedih tur bangras?	14	27%
6	Apa krana sebun I Sangsiah kabesbes?	11	21%
7	Tekén nyén I Sangsiah nguningang solahné IBojog?	2	4%
8	Dija I Kedis Sangsiah ngaé sebun?	39	75%
9	Apa krana kenehné I Sangsiah nyangtangsebet?	3	6%
10	Kénkén I Bojog ngajum awakné?	2	4%

From Table 1, the pretest results were obtained with 10 items with an average score of 23 out of a maximum score of 100.

Result and Discussion

The result of this research is to produce interactive multimedia about Satua I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah, with the media displayed as follows:

Figure 1: Splash Screen Page

Figure 2. Start Screen Page

Figure 3. Main Menu Info Page

Picture 8. Puzzle Page

Figure 4. Page Starting Mai Mace Satua

Figure 9. Playing Puzzle Page

Figure 5. Materials page of Mai Mace Satua

Figure 6. Quiz Homepage

Figure 7. Quiz page

After the interactive multimedia development process, the testing stage was carried out in the form of questionnaires and post-tests on 24 students from class V SDN 03 Sempidi regarding Balinese language material. The results of the questionnaire are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Student Questionnaire Results

No.	Question	Index (%)
1	Is learning satua with interactive multimedia interesting?	89,17
2	Is the interactive multimedia display appropriate for the material?	86,67%
3	Were you able to do the exercises?	79,17%
4	Can you tell the difference between good and bad characters?	92,50%
5	Were you able to understand the storyline and the message?	85,83%
6	Is the sound in the interactive multimedia clear and appropriate?	77,50%
7	Do the characters in the interactive multimedia fit the story?	85,00%
8	Has the interactive multimedia increased your interest in learning?	89,17%
9	Are the animated images clear	94,17%
10	Is this interactive multimedia animation recommended for continued airing and distribution?	91,67%

Maximum Poin = 1200

Total Poin = 1045

Indeks (%) = $1045/1200 \times 100\% = 87\%$

The results of the questionnaire against the students of V grade SDN 03 Sempidi stated "Very Good" with the delivery of information on interactive multimedia Satua I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah according to the learning. As for the evaluation or post-test values of the quiz, you can see them in Table 3.

Tabel 3. Student Post Test Results

Absence number	1	2	3	4	5	6
Value	60	80	80	70	80	80
Absence number	7	8	10	11	13	14
Value	80	80	60	70	70	80
Absence number	15	17	19	20	21	22
Value	80	80	80	80	70	80
Absence number	23	24	25	26	27	28
Value	80	80	80	80	70	70

Maximum Poin = 2400

Total Poin = 1820

Indeks (%) = $1820/2400 \times 100\% = 75,83\%$

From the evaluation results, 24 students got an average score of 75.83, compared to the pre-test score of 23. From these scores, it can be concluded that students experienced an increase in understanding of the material and motivation.

Conclusion

From the results of this research, it can be concluded that interactive multimedia that contains material satua with two languages, namely language Bali and Indonesian language, quizzes, and games played an active role in helping students of class V SDN 03 Sempidi understand the learning material of language Bali through Satua I Bojog Teken I Sangsiah, as seen by the significant rise in post-test values compared to pre-test scores.

Acknowledgments

This article is based on the problems that occurred in SDN 03 Sempidi related to the understanding of V-class students of Bali language subjects. The author is grateful for the input and advice from readers and the editorial team for the optimality of this article.

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